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Dr Martin Melin, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Alnarp, Sweden

WEBSITE:

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Nextfood - Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system

Practice Abstract #10: Action learning Agriscapes: Enhanced extension service to young farmers based on principles and practices of the Action Learning method

Author: Chrysanthi Charatsari, American Farm School of Thessaloniki, Greece

In the Greek case study, the methodology of action learning is employed to create groups of heterogeneous actors (learning sets) who engage in collective, discovery-based learning activities, to collaboratively construct new knowledge. In total, three different learning sets have been formed: (1) livestock farming; (2) viticulture; and (3) food processing companies. Each one of the first two groups consists of a farmer, a student of agronomy, an academic, a professional with work experience in the field, and an observer with expertise in knowledge co-production processes. Through a process of discovering problems, proposing and implementing solutions, and reflecting on the procedure of identifying-solving problems, each learning set intends to develop a common understanding of the ways farming is practiced as well as to discover different meanings of farming and agricultural sustainability. This way, each participant helps others to make sense of their experience, while the dialogue and the reflection process leads to a redefinition of the concept of farming. Within this context, students are trying to develop their communication skills, their reflection competencies and their problem-solving skills.

Based on the above-mentioned findings and the principles of action learning, a course has been designed and organized and will be held at International Hellenic University during the current semester. The course's curriculum is action-based oriented and after its first implementation and after an assessment process some changes and/or improvements will be carried out in order the students to be more actively engaged in the learning process and to be more competent in terms of communication and problem-solving skills.